

A inclusion model based on activity: fitting work tasks to people with disabilities

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Abstract This article presents an Inclusion model based on the activity for people with disabilities into work and discusses the results of its application. The methods and techniques of this model are based on the methodological and theoretical frameworks of Ergonomic Work Analysis (EWA), of the Social Model of Disability and of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health. The model aims to analyze people with disabilities, looking at individual capabilities, knowledge, barriers and facilitators to carry out activities. EWA may associate factors such - workstations design, postures demanded by work tasks, movements, technical requirements and the necessary knowledge – to the individuals course of action. The analysis of people with disabilities and the understanding of work activities are the guiding principles that underpin the practice for inclusion process, aiming to assist individuals in developing their ability to work, related to the qualification demands to perform effectively, and the tasks set by the work organization. The research was developed in São Paulo/Brazil between 2009 and 2012. The study included 131 people with disabilities in a multinational metallurgical company. There was a prevalence of male participants with physical disabilities, and age between 36-45 years old. We noted that, in this company, the work activities were compatible with the people's limitations and potential, allowing the inclusion into the workplace. The most part of the workers (62.5%) were able to perform tasks aimed to assemble small components developed in the stands, with areas of appropriate scope and possibility of alternation of posture, sitting or standing. 3.81% were oriented to the participation in cooperative systems of work and 33.69% were oriented for traineeship in other companies. The contribution for the inclusion process of the model may be explained due to the situated knowledge issued from EWA realized before hiring people by the company.